

WORKSHEET – INNOVATIVE COMPANIES

Innovative Companies

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Lead-in activity

Nowadays, companies need to be innovative to stay ahead of their competitors.

- Carry out some research on the internet and find an innovative company.
- Be prepared to explain why you think this company is innovative and why you've chosen this particular company. You have 15 minutes for this task.
- Then get together in pairs and discuss the companies you've found with your partner. This task should take 10 minutes.
- Your teacher will then ask you to share your thoughts in class.

Please note: Try to use English sources for your research!

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Innovative companies – example

TED-TALK

- Go to YouTube and watch the TED-talk "The unexpected benefit of celebrating failure" by Astro Teller.
- Then answer the questions below.

Please note: A moonshot factory, like X or Google X, pursues big dreams and visions.

1. The moonshot blueprint is based on (choose the correct options):

- huge problems
- radical solutions
- existing solutions
- breakthrough technology

2. Find the right words to fill the gaps:

According to Astro Teller, Google X is a _____ place. Among the projects they killed was a project about automated _____ farming. At X, employees kill projects and are _____ and _____ for it.

3. Writing Task

What do you think about this moonshot factory and how they deal with ideas, projects and problems? Explain your opinion and give examples. Write 250 words.

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Notes for teachers

Topic:	<i>Innovations, innovative companies</i>
Number of students:	<i>10-30</i>
Instructions for teacher:	<i>This is a worksheet that contains exercises about innovations and innovative companies. It can be used for synchronous teaching sessions and homework assignments.</i>

Answer Key:

1. The moonshot blueprint is based on (choose the correct options):

X huge problems

X radical solutions

_ existing solutions

X breakthrough technology

2. Find the right words to fill the gaps:

According to Astro Teller, Google X is a [messy] place. Among the projects they killed was a project about automated [vertical] farming. At X, employees kill projects and are [rewarded] and [promoted] for it.